

ISAC meets O-RAN: a RIC service to ensure sensing delay requirements

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Abstract—Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) is a key enabler for 6G technology, expected to drive new services and enhance the quality and efficiency of wireless communications. To this end, this paper showcases the integration of sensing information into the Open RAN (O-RAN) architecture by extending the E2 Service Models (E2SMs) through the FlexRIC implementation. The proposed E2SM aggregates the capability of monitoring both the physical environment and the statistics derived from the sensing data, while also enabling control over the sensing-Radio Unit (sRU). Moreover, since the traffic generated by the sRU may vary depending on the use of the sensing data, it must meet strict latency and freshness requirements defined by each use case. For this aim, we propose the use of a Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controller to dynamically adjust the capacity assigned to the sensing slice, ensuring that the transmitted information remains timely and up to date.

Index Terms—Sensing, RIC, xApp, JSAC, 5G, 6G, ISAC

I. INTRODUCTION

The Open RAN (O-RAN) ecosystem fosters an open, intelligent, programmable and virtualized paradigm of mobile networks. With the aim of furnishing the network with intelligence, Key Performance Indicators (KPI) exchange between different nodes and architectural elements is enabled. Given this approach, adhering to standardized interfaces is fundamental to guarantee the applicability of the proposed solutions and foster interoperability among components and vendors. One of the key components in the O-RAN architecture is the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC), a functionality based on the *software-defined networking* paradigm that provides a centralized control point for the Radio Access Network (RAN). The E2 Application Protocol (E2AP) protocol is proposed to facilitate the communication between the RIC and the RAN. It is responsible for encapsulating messages according to defined Service Models (SMs) and establishing a standardized communication mechanism between the eXtended App (xApp), which runs on top of Near-Real-Time RAN Intelligent Controller (Near-RT RIC) and whose purpose is the automation of the RAN. In turn, the E2 Service Model (E2SM) specification defines the common elements associated with each of the procedures of the E2AP protocol [1], [2].

In particular, O-RAN defines five SM: (i) RAN Function Network Interface (NI), which exposes the network interfaces; (ii) Key Performance Metrics (KPM), which monitors the statistics of the E2 nodes; (iii) RAN Control (RC), which defines the interface to control the Radio Bearers, map Quality

of Service (QoS) flows to Data Rate Bearers (DRBs), manage radio resource allocation, control connected-mode mobility, manage radio access mechanisms (for instance, dual connectivity, carrier aggregation), among other functionalities; (iv) Cell Configuration and Control (CCC), which enables control and monitoring of cell configurations; and (v) Lower Layer Control (LLC) to control lower-layers of the RAN, while collecting channel and traffic information and managing scheduling and precoding parameters.

Additionally, other SMs have been defined based on 3GPP specifications, such as those for the MAC, RLC and PDCP layers [3]. Likewise, [4] proposes a customized SM for Traffic Control (TC) compatible with O-RAN. Specifically, a traffic control pipeline is introduced in the user plane, located between the SDAP and PDCP layers, and comprising the following functions: *classifier, policer, queue, scheduler, shaper, and pacer blocks*; it thus defines an E2SM that encapsulates these information elements.

Furthermore, the IMT-2030 framework, which identifies requirements for the next generation of wireless communications, highlights the integration of communications with network sensing capabilities, known as Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC), with the aim of enabling network intelligence based on the collected information. Several studies have addressed the vision, techniques and applications arising from the integration of sensing and communications in 6G. Previous research has analyzed potential architectures for incorporating ISAC, as well as the most relevant KPIs, identifying the challenges associated with its implementation and proposing solutions to address them, including enabling technologies and standardization aspects [5]–[7].

The authors of [8] and [9] discuss the benefits, technical challenges, and potential applications of ISAC, such as connected vehicles, environmental monitoring and smart homes. They highlight the current state of development and standardization, as well as the trade-offs that need to be considered when sharing wireless resources between sensing and communication functions. Additionally, ISAC’s role in improving efficiency, precise localization, and environmental perception is emphasized, along with various techniques, architectures, and applications for accurate mapping and situational awareness.

To achieve a complete and effective integration of communication and sensing, it is necessary to incorporate sensing elements within the O-RAN architecture, so that they can be

managed jointly with communication entities. This approach will allow both informed decision-making and comprehensive monitoring of the physical environment. However, previous studies have largely overlooked the integration of non-3GPP and 3GPP technologies within the O-RAN framework to improve sensing accuracy, leveraging a wide range of frequencies, from sub-6GHz (meter-level resolution, corresponding to FR1) and cmWave (FR2, tens of centimeters) to mmWave (sub-10cm resolution), while assessing the resulting impact on overall network performance.

To address this gap, we propose and implement a sensing SM with the capacity to send either: (i) semi-processed data in the form of Estimated Channel Coefficients (CHEs) (considering the trade-off against sending raw OFDM symbols); or (ii) fully processed data (for instance heatmaps). Furthermore, the SM permits configuring the sensing resolution and information exchange. On top of it, in order to manage respond to the variability of sensing traffic, as a consequence of the potential configuration, a closed-loop traffic controller is proposed and validated. All in all, the main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- We extend the collection of E2SMs by defining and implemented a new one for real traffic sensing, and sensing capabilities control.
- We design and develop an xApp to orchestrate the sensing information flow from the sensing-Radio Unit (sRU), enabling the monitoring of network-level metrics, such as the End-to-End (E2E) delay across the E2 interface, as well as sensing data that capture the physical environment status.
- We integrate a network controller, based on a Proportional–Integral–Derivative (PID) mechanism, capable of dynamically adjusting the capacity allocated to the E2E sensing slice, according to the requirements of the active use case, thereby ensuring the freshness of the sensed information, guaranteeing that the corresponding delay requirement of critical applications is met [10].
- All our development, including the modified FlexRIC, as well as the sRU emulators, have been made available to the research community¹. The repository includes all scenario configuration and processing utilities, to further ensure the reproducibility of the results discussed in the paper.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews the state of the art and identifies the research gap we address in this work. Section III introduces the key concepts leveraged to enable joint sensing and communication. Section IV presents both the system integration and the validation of each component. Finally, Section V summarizes the insights gained from this study and outlines the future research directions emerging from it.

II. STATE OF ART

Several works focus on the timeliness of sensing information for critical applications. Xu et al. [11] optimize Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)-assisted networks to minimize the Peak Age of Information (PAoI) by jointly adjusting UAV’s position, sensing duration, communication time and power allocation, enhancing both sensing and communication performance. Sarupriya et al. [12] propose ultra-reliable, low-latency ISAC system designs for critical applications, emphasizing dynamic resource allocation to ensure timely and dependable operations. The authors of [13] analyze the upper bound of sensory data transmission delay in ISAC networks, using stochastic network calculus and spatial modeling of sensing infrastructures. An optimal power allocation strategy is also proposed to minimize delay, while balancing sensing quality and transmission latency.

On the other hand, several works have used the FlexRIC implementation to make sensing-related information available. For instance, the authors of [14], introduce ORAN-Sense, an architecture for locating non-cooperative transmitters using Internet of Things (IoT) spectrum sensors integrated into 5G networks through O-RAN. It employs Time Difference of Arrival (TDOA) algorithms with clock offset correction and synchronization based on signals of opportunity, implemented as an xApp within the RIC. Rego et. al [15] propose a prototype of Near-RT RIC xApps for flexible ML-based spectrum sensing. Their work evinces how the combination of O-RAN open architecture and GNU Radio can be leveraged to implement and test spectrum sensing algorithms for research, education, and small-scale applications.

Finally, the following works explore PID-based control mechanisms for adaptive network management. Chatzistefanidis et al. [16] propose LLM-assisted “symbiotic agents” that dynamically tune a P-controller to improve radio access management and SLA negotiation, enhancing efficiency and robustness. In the same line, Wang et al. [17] introduce a PID-based rate control scheme for UAV-IoT slicing, adjusting per-hop transmission rates to meet end-to-end performance goals.

To the best of our knowledge, there are no previous works studying the impact of real sensing traffic on network performance in practical testbeds and architectures. We have not either found any previous paper proposing techniques to ensure E2E delay bounds for sensing information that satisfy stringent application requirements. These two aspects, which are crucial to fully exploit ISAC-enabled networks are specifically addressed in this paper.

III. O-RAN ISAC ARCHITECTURE

The proposed architecture extends the O-RAN framework by integrating both active and passive sensing elements within a multi-RAT environment, as illustrated in Fig. 1. This design combines 5G-RAN and non-3GPP connectivity (Sub-6 GHz, Wi-Fi, mmWave, radar) to enable accurate environmental perception. Sensing information, obtained through Channel State Information (CSI)-based or passive radar approaches, is exposed to the RAN via the E2 interface of the RIC.

¹<https://github.com/tlmat-unican/sensing-flexric-controller.git>

This way, the sensing devices are seen by the Near-RT RIC as regular E2 nodes, similar to the Open-Central Unit (O-CU), Open-Distributed Unit (O-DU), or monolithic base station deployments (e.g., gNB, eNB). Data exchange follows a publish-subscribe mechanism, facilitating interaction between xApps and RAN functions or sensing units sRU, corresponding to non-3GPP technologies devoted to environmental perception tasks.

Fig. 1: O-RAN architecture with sensing devices.

A. mmWave RADAR

For this work, we employ the solution described in [18]. It is a real-time mmWave ISAC system capable of bidirectional data transmission up to 5.8 Gbps, combined with monostatic Radio Detection and Ranging (RADAR) detection, which provides a range resolution of 6.7 cm and a maximum sensing rate of 2.1 kHz. The system is built on an mmWave Software-Defined Radio (SDR) platform operating in the 60 GHz band, extended with a real-time OFDM baseband processor and additional components to support ISAC functionality. Key hardware elements include the AMD ZCU111 evaluation board with high-speed data converters, as well as dual phased-array antenna modules for beam steering in the $\pm 45^\circ$ angular range. In this implementation, the system operates at a sensing rate of 100 Hz, requiring a data transfer rate of 156.5 Mbps to collect the CHEs. The CHEs comprise of 63 beams, covering different angular directions, and 1024 subcarriers, 828 of which are used for channel estimation. Following post-processing, a 1024-point inverse Fast Fourier Transform (iFFT) is applied to the CHEs from all 63 beams, producing an environmental heatmap represented as a 63×128 (angle \times range) matrix with double-precision resolution [18].

B. FlexRIC

Intelligence within the network is provided through two control loops: the Near-RT RIC, operating on millisecond-to-second timescales to optimize RAN behavior via the E2 interface, and the Non-Real-Time RAN Intelligent Controller (Non-RT RIC), which handles long-term policy management, analytics, and resource optimization through the A1 interface. The Non-RT RIC is integrated into the Service Management

and Orchestration (SMO) framework, ensuring efficient system configuration and performance management through the O1 interface.

This work focuses on extending the Near-RT RIC to support sensing data exchange, regardless of how it was originally obtained. The E2 interface, instantiated over Stream Transmission Control Protocol (SCTP), supports two key services, E2AP and E2SM, enabling E2 nodes to publish data while xApps in the Near-RT RIC subscribe to specific RAN functions. E2 communication is structured in terms of services, procedures and Information Elements (IEs), which define the data types and ranges exchanged between the Near-RT RIC and E2 nodes.

Within the E2AP protocol, different procedures encapsulate E2SMs, implementing control and monitoring functionalities. Two main categories are distinguished: *Global Procedures* (e.g., E2 Setup) and *Near-RT RIC Functional Procedures* (e.g., Subscription Request, Subscription Delete, Indication). Each RAN function is defined by its corresponding SM, which specifies available services such as *report*, *insert*, *control*, *policy*, and *query*. To enable the transmission of sensing data, a new SM was designed and implemented, following the E2 communication framework, using the OAI FlexRIC.²

C. PID

The PID controller is a classical feedback-based control mechanism widely employed in systems that require continuous regulation and automatic correction of their behavior [19]. It operates by setting an error value as the difference between a desired setpoint and a measured process variable, to afterwards adjust the control input to minimize this error over time. In the context of this work, the PID controller generates a control signal $u(t)$ that determines the capacity assigned to a specific network slice, denoted as $r(t+1)$. The control variable in this case is the E2E delay measured at the E2 interface, while the setpoint d_{ref} captures the target delay value. The controller adjusts $r(t)$ according to the error $e(t) = d_{ref} - d(t)$ between the desired delay and the measured delay, dynamically maintaining the delay within target bounds, despite network fluctuations. Specifically, $r(t+1)$ is determined as:

$$I(t) = \Delta t \sum_{i=1}^k e(t_i), \quad D(t) = \frac{e(t) - e(t-1)}{\Delta t}, \quad (1a)$$

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i I(t) + K_d D(t), \quad (1b)$$

$$r(t+1) = r(t) + u(t) \quad (1c)$$

where $u(t)$ is the control action, $r(t)$ corresponds to the previously assigned rate, and $r(t+1)$ is the capacity determined by the PID controller, which is fed back to the upstream sensing process for dynamic adjustment, according to the system requirements. The reminder terms in Eq. (1b) correspond to parts of the PID controller (in practice, a

²<https://gitlab.eurecom.fr/mosaic5g/flexric.git>

rectangular approximation of the required integration is used, as can be seen in Eq. (1a).

The proportional term compensates for the instantaneous deviation between measured and target delays d_{ref} . The integral term accumulates past errors to eliminate steady-state offsets, while the derivative term accounts for the rate of the delay change, thereby enhancing transient response and system stability. The gains K_p , K_i , and K_d govern the respective contributions of the proportional, integral, and derivative components, and are tuned according to the desired performance criteria.

IV. SYSTEM INTEGRATION AND VALIDATION

This section presents the system integration along with the corresponding validation results obtained from the testbed shown in Fig. 1. First, to make sensing information available at the RIC, a new sensing-oriented SM has been developed and integrated, as a library, into all involved agents, namely the Near-RT RIC, the xApps, and the E2 agent. The sensing information is encapsulated within a new SM, included in the `Indication` message. It is sent as heatmaps, characterized by angular and range dimensions, resolution and signal strength, with the latter transmitted as a binary buffer until fully received at the xApp. Furthermore, several sensing control commands, including `select_angle`, `select_radio`, `select_refresh_rate`, and `select_resolution`, are defined following a Type-Length-Value (TLV) format, which allows their integration within a single RIC Control message. These functionalities are supported by specific internal logic adaptations in each entity. On the E2 node, data from the sensing processing unit can be received and locally processed to generate lightweight sensing information, thereby minimizing network load when the processing unit is hosted remotely. The E2 node includes an agent responsible for receiving the data, and parsing it into the corresponding format defined by the SM. Finally, the xApps collects the data through `Indication` callbacks and stores it in a MySQL database for subsequent analysis. Furthermore, the xApps has been enhanced with the capability to issue sensing control commands toward the sRU, based on predefined logic or decision criteria.

Fig. 2 illustrates the evolution of throughput over time as Control commands are issued via the E2 interface from the xApp to the E2 node. In our validation scenario, the system is configured with a fixed 100 Mbps rate (enforced using `tc-netem` on the outgoing queue of the Ethernet device) and a Maximum Transmission Unit (MTU) of 9000 B, assuming network support for jumbo frames. Initially, a heatmap of approximately 65 kB (in `double` precision) is transmitted, with a refresh rate of 100 Hz. Subsequently, the resolution is reduced to `float`, which leads to a proportional reduction in both throughput and delay. Next, a narrower range of angles and distances is selected, resulting in a smaller data payload of around 10 kB (`float`). Finally, the resolution

is increased again, causing both throughput and delay to increase (≈ 20 kB). Overall, the results show that greater packet fragmentation leads to additional delay due to micro-bursts, while a baseline latency remains inherent to the traversal of the different components within the RIC.

Fig. 2: Evolution of sensing throughput and delay under configuration changes triggered by RIC Control messages.

After successfully validating the expected performance of the sRU when interacting with the Near-RT RIC, we address the control of the corresponding latency. In this sense, motivated by the amount of data generated by the sRU as well as the specific use case requirements, we design a PID controller that assigns a rate to the corresponding slice, based on the delay experienced by the sensing information. We integrate the proposed algorithm, depicted in Alg. 1, as shown in Fig. 1. This communication is provisioned over a separate isolated network, which mimics the O1 interface. After gathering new sensing information (`Indication` messages, line (2) Alg. 1) and considering an observation interval T_{change} , we obtain the average delay experienced during that slot (sampling period $T_{\text{change}} = \Delta t$). This information, together with the target delay and the observation interval, is then used to compute the PID, as can be seen in line (9) of Alg. 1. Based on the PID output, the corresponding rate (which is inversely proportional to the delay) is computed and subsequently limited, according to the physical constraints of the devices (bounded by a maximum and minimum capacity). Finally, this rate is sent (O1 interface) to reconfigure the network to achieve the required delay. In practice, we perform this reconfiguration through the traffic control associated with the E2 interface.

Next, we evaluate the performance of the PID controller, based on the configuration summarized in Table I. Fig. 3 illustrates the rate evolution, set by the PID controller (red) alongside the delay experienced by the new sensing information for our target flow (refresh rate 50 Hz, 32 kB heatmap). During the first 20 s, only the target flow is active. Starting at a rate of 10 Mbps, the PID controller successfully adjusts the rate to satisfy the specified delay requirement (yellow line). Subsequently, a background flow (for which no metrics are collected) is introduced to the same slice during the following 20 s interval, indicated by the shaded zone in Fig. 3, with a refresh rate of 100 Hz and the default heatmap size. When this happens, the PID controller exhibits transient oscillations initially, before converging to a new rate that

maintains the delay close to the target. In the subsequent 20 s, the background flow reduces its heatmap resolution (shown by a brownish color), thereby decreasing the injected rate. We can see how the the PID controller is able to correspondingly adapt the rate, meeting the desired delay. Finally, upon termination of the background flow, the PID controller restores the rate to its initial value.

TABLE I: Configuration of the evaluation setup.

Testbed Components and Functions	
Beelink Mini S12 Pro	xApp & Near-RT RIC
Asus NUC 12 Pro	E2 Processor, Agent & Controller
mmWave RADAR	2.1 kHz max. rate; 6.7 cm resolution
MTU	9000B
Parameter	Value
Application duration	120 sec.
Sensing refresh rate	Target = 50 Hz, Background = 100 Hz
Heatmap size	65 kB (double), 32 kB (float)
E2 latency (target)	{80, 60, 40} ms
PID parameters	$K_p = 1, K_i = 0.02, K_d = 0.1$
Sampling period (T_{change})	1 sec.
Validation E2 interface rate	100 Mbps (tc-netem)

Algorithm 1 Sensing Slice Control Logic

Input: RIC message rd , T_{change} , d_{ref} , R_{min} , R_{max}

- 1: $now \leftarrow time_now_us()$
- 2: **if** $t_{prev} == rd.ind.new_sm.msg.timestamp$ **then return**
- 3: **end if**
- 4: $t_{prev} \leftarrow rd.ind.new_sm.msg.timestamp$
- 5: $d_sum += now - rd.ind.new_sm.msg.timestamp$
- 6: $d_cnt += 1$
- 7: **if** $now - t_{last} \geq T_{change}$ **then**
- 8: $d_avg \leftarrow d_sum/d_cnt$
- 9: $pid_out \leftarrow compute(d_{ref}, L_{avg}, T_{change})$
- 10: $R \leftarrow clip(R - pid_out, R_{min}, R_{max})$
- 11: change_slice_rate(R)
- 12: $t_{last} \leftarrow now$
- 13: $d_sum, d_cnt \leftarrow 0$
- 14: **end if**

Second, Fig. 4 illustrates the behavior of the target flow when a background flow periodically changes its heatmap size (from 65 kB to 32 kB, repeatedly), according to a pace that is swept, and captured along the x-axis. On its right, the figure shows (in red) the reference value of the target flow, when non background traffic is considered. As can be observed, the addition of a background flow increases the variability of the target flow, but the PID controller ensures that the average value remains at the target value, thus maintaining the delay requirements.

Finally, in Fig. 5 we evaluate the performance of the PID controller when the target delay (yellowish line) varies over the observation period, mimicking the introduction of new services with stricter latency requirements within a specific slice. As shown in Fig. 5, the controller dynamically adjusts the capacity assigned to the slice: when the target delay is

Fig. 3: Evolution of the rate selected by the PID controller and the delay experienced by the sensing information for the target flow.

Fig. 4: Target flow behavior under a background flow with periodically changing heatmap.

reduced, the instantaneous error $e(t)$ becomes more negative, prompting the proportional term $K_p e(t)$ to increase the control action, thereby raising the allocated capacity and keeping the measured delay close to the target. Conversely, when the target delay increases, the magnitude of the error gets lower and the control action decreases the capacity. As can be seen, oscillations around the setpoint become more pronounced when the target is relaxed, mainly due to the looser delay requirement and the relatively high proportional gain K_p . This behavior highlights the intrinsic trade-off between responsiveness and stability in PID delay control.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This work presents one of the first fully operational integration of sensing and communications in future mobile networks (6G) within the O-RAN architecture. To this end, we have discussed how the sensing element interacts with the network from an architectural perspective, explored the implications of implementing this functionality in real networks, and deployed a test scenario. The results presented in this work highlight several key insights regarding the management of sensing traffic in near real-time network slices. First, the load injected by sRU (for instance radars or other sources) can

Fig. 5: Capacity assigned by the PID controller (red) and resulting delay (green) as the target delay (yellow line) varies over time.

be highly variable, and so imposes significant demands on the network. Proper slice dimensioning therefore requires not only a deep understanding of traffic patterns and their accurate characterization, but also how such traffic interacts with IP networks.

In order to manage sensing slice dimensioning, we have proposed the integration of a controller, based on PID. The results evince that it is able to appropriately adapt the underlying network resources to meet the strict delay requirements, which are of the utmost relevance to fully exploit the benefits brought by sensing information.

As a future line of work, we will extend the SM equipping it with additional configuration options, including the capability to select the processing level of sensing information (i.e. sending heatmaps or CHEs). We will also explore the possibility to extend standard SMs, such as LLC, to support sensing information.

As for control of sensing slices, we will look at enhancing the PID controller’s performance, by integrating it with an AI-based meta-optimizer that dynamically tunes the controller’s K -parameters to adapt to variable channel conditions.

The processing of information extracted by radars can be significantly impacted by communication protocols, due to packet fragmentation and reassembly mechanisms, being particularly relevant in publish-subscribe communication models. We will study compression algorithms to minimize the additional delay induced by such processes as well as coordination of sensing telemetry considering communication capacity.

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